

Data Granularity Use Cases

Supporting Output

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Abstract: Data infrastructure can be built around predefined levels of granularity for data, for which conventions vary. The appropriate level of granularity can optimize discovery, access, interoperability, analysis, identification, citation, curation, and more. These use cases developed by the Research Data Alliance (RDA) Data Granularity Working Group (WG), along with its Guidance Document, provide priority use cases for research data infrastructure providers and other key stakeholders. The use cases are presented in two (otherwise identical) file formats: a readonly PDF for browsing, and an Excel file with additional functionality (such as filtering); each file contains detailed descriptions and instructions for use.

Impact: These use cases will help data professionals to determine and deploy the best level of granularity for supporting data across the lifecycle. The key beneficiaries of the use cases include: data producers (more efficient data management, greater ability to track value and use of subsets of data), data infrastructure providers (enhanced user services, clarity on the levels of data granularity on which to operate, greater ease in exchange of subsets of data (and metadata) with other systems, secondary data users (faster discovery and access of data of interest, expanded research possibilities given new ways to work with granular), and the public (benefits from faster and more sophisticated research produced). Furthermore, given the integral, cross-cutting nature of granularity across a range of issues, a prime value of this output is having leveraged and built upon existing and ongoing RDA work amongst a range of groups.

Contribution to United Nations SDGs: These use cases will enable the improvement of research infrastructure and the efficient creation and use of research data resources, by institutions working both individually and in partnership. Such improvements in turn will enable further and better research and knowledge in all of the SDG areas.

Language: English

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RDA webpage: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/data-granularity-wg/activity/>

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Introduction

Title: Data Granularity Use Cases

Output Type: Working Group Supporting Output

Authors: Katherine McNeill, Graham Smith, Guangyuan Sun, Beverley Jones, David Elbert, Rouven Schabinger, Maggie Hellström

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Instructions for Understanding and Utilising the Data Granularity Use Cases Spreadsheet

This Use Cases spreadsheet was created as a final deliverable of the RDA Data Granularity Working Group (<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/data-granularity-wg>), as a Supporting Output to inform its Guidance Document on Data Granularity.

Explanation of Tabs

Use Case List: First main informative tab, which lists structured Use Cases in the following user story format: 'As a [role/who] I want to [goal/what] so that [benefit to be achieved/why]'. Each case has a numeric identifier and is described according to structured fields. Note that user stories may be repeated across rows, if a use case has multiple relevant values for any of the structured fields (Role, Category/Type of Use, Level of granularity), as structured fields only accept one value. These cases may be actual use cases encountered or representative of a wider user group/problem. Some, but not necessarily all, of these use cases stem from narratives (overall scenario descriptions) cross-referenced on the Narratives tab.

Narratives: Second main informative tab. Primary purpose: free-text descriptions of scenarios in which data granularity is a factor. Where applicable, Narrative numbers are cross-referenced to the Use Cases List tab. Note: given the more flexible free-text format of the Narratives, there will be information in the Narratives (and even entire Narratives themselves) not reflected in the structured Use Case List. Secondary purpose: to list documents from which use cases were pulled, in a row as if it were a narrative (thus the Narrative identifier links a use case to its source document).

Concept Definitions: defines values for any controlled field on Use Case List.

Summary Table: Frequency analysis of use cases, to inform guidance paper.

Creation Process: Instructions followed by Use Case authors regarding the standardized process for creation, including list of authors.

Instructions for Use

1. View the Use Case List sheet in order to understand specific user scenarios regarding granularity. The sheet can be reviewed in its entirety or filtered by any of the controlled columns: Role, Level of Granularity, Category/Type of Use.
2. Consult the Concept Definitions sheet to further understand the concepts utilized on the Use Case Sheet. Consult the Creation Process sheet to understand the process of authors to create Use Cases.
3. Read the Narratives tab understand overall scenarios and source documents involving data granularity (some of which is presented in a structured way on Use Case List).
4. Review the Summary Table to understand the frequency of different types of use cases.

Use Case	Role/Who	Primary Goal/What	Motivation/Why	Level(s) of	Category/Type
Serial #	As a [role/who]	I want to [goal/what]	So that [benefit to be	Controlled field, from	Controlled field, from
UC001	Data Consumer	Find data of interest to	Quickly find things	Variable	Findability/Discovery
UC002	Data Consumer	Download just the data	Save both time and	Custom subset	Access
UC003	Data Consumer	Combine data files	Answer research	Variable	Analysis
UC004	Data Consumer	Combine data files	Answer research	Custom combination	Analysis
UC005	Repository	Have robust SEO that	Users find our data,	Variable	Findability/Discovery
UC006	Repository	Have robust SEO that	Users find our data,	Dataset	Findability/Discovery
UC007	Repository	Enable users to	Readers can learn	Variable	Access
UC008	Repository	Enable users to	Readers can learn	Custom subset	Identification/Citation/M
UC009	Data Producer	Share the data	To make my	Custom combination	Curation/Deposit/Pres
UC010	Data Producer	Appropriately cite the	To make my	Custom combination	Identification/Citation/M
UC011	Data Consumer	Have a thumbnail	Assess the	File	Other
UC012	Data Consumer	file, for example 10 lines	Assess the	Custom subset	Findability/Discovery
UC013	Data Consumer	collected by educational	Gain an	Collection (of datasets)	Analysis
UC014	Data Consumer	As a researcher, I want	Assess the	File	Other
UC015	Data Consumer	Get an overview of	Determine which	Collection (of datasets)	Findability/Discovery
UC016	Data Consumer	Receive information on	Save time to get an	Collection (of datasets)	Findability/Discovery
UC017	Data Consumer	Have an overview of	Analyze them	Dataset	Findability/Discovery
UC018	Data Consumer	Have an overview of	Analyze them	Variable	Analysis
UC019	Data Consumer	Get an overview of	Evaluate their	Dataset	Findability/Discovery
UC020	Data Producer	Track different versions	Understand exactly	Dataset	Curation/Deposit/Pres
UC021	Data Producer	Publish multiple	Publish various	Dataset	Curation/Deposit/Pres
UC022	Data Consumer	Find multiple datasets	Find various	Dataset	Findability/Discovery
UC023	Data Producer	Publish my software	Share and get credit	File	Curation/Deposit/Pres
UC024	Data Consumer	Find software code in a	Re-use others' code	File	Findability/Discovery
UC025	Data Producer	Version and timestamp	Identify relevant	Custom subset	Identification/Citation/M
UC026	Data Consumer	Retrieve new updates to	Find, access, and	Custom subset	Access
UC027	Repository	Measure the size of my	Provide accurate and	Most/all	Other
UC028	Data Consumer	Cite a dataset that I	Ensure my results	Custom subset	Identification/Citation/M
UC029	Data Consumer	Access the specific	Ensure that the data	Custom subset	Access
UC030	Repository	versioning to ensure	Uniquely identify	Custom subset	Curation/Deposit/Pres
UC031	Repository	Timestamping: Ensure	Uniquely identify	Custom subset	Curation/Deposit/Pres
UC032	Repository	Query Store Facilities:	Uniquely identify	Custom subset	Curation/Deposit/Pres

UC033	Repository	Query Uniqueness: Re-	Uniquely identify	Custom subset	Curation/Deposit/Pres
UC034	Repository	Stable Sorting and	Uniquely identify	Custom subset	Curation/Deposit/Pres
UC035	Repository	Query Timestamping:	Uniquely identify	Custom subset	Curation/Deposit/Pres
UC036	Repository	Query PID: Assign a	Citations can include	Custom subset	Identification/Citation/M
UC037	Repository	Store Query: Store	Uniquely identify	Custom subset	Curation/Deposit/Pres
UC038	Repository	Automated Citation	Data consumers can	Custom subset	Identification/Citation/M
UC039	Repository	Landing Page: Make the	Data consumers can	Custom subset	Access
UC040	Repository	Machine Actionability:	Systems can be	Custom subset	Access
UC041	Repository	Technology Migration	Our support for	Custom subset	Curation/Deposit/Pres
UC042	Repository	Report usage data at a	Support	Dataset	Identification/Citation/M
UC043	Repository	Retrieve usage data with	More easily analyze	Dataset	Identification/Citation/M
UC044	Repository	usage of data we hold,	The repository can	Dataset	Identification/Citation/M
UC045	Data Producer	Understand the extent to	Both understand	Dataset	Identification/Citation/M
UC046	Research Admini	Understand the extent to	Demonstrate the	Dataset	Identification/Citation/M
UC047	Funder	Understand the extent to	Understand the	Dataset	Identification/Citation/M
UC048	Data manager/st	Decide at what level of	Enable the	Most/all	Curation/Deposit/Pres
UC049	Data manager/st	Decide at what level of	Efficiently manage	Most/all	Curation/Deposit/Pres
UC050	Data Producer	Make my data available	Machine learning	Custom combination	Interoperability
UC051	Data Consumer	Have a single-entry	I can easily select	Dataset	Findability/Discovery
UC052	Data Consumer	Have a single-entry	I can easily select	Collection (of datasets)	Findability/Discovery
UC053	Data Consumer	Find the links between a	Investigate these	Dataset	Findability/Discovery
UC054	Data Consumer	Understand the	Determine if the	Variable	Access
UC055	Data Consumer	Understand the	Determine if the	Dataset	Access
UC056	Data Consumer	Understand the	Determine if the	Instrument (of data collector	Access
UC057	Data Consumer	Filter a data search	I can know which	Dataset	Findability/Discovery
UC058	Data Consumer	Filter a data search	I can know which	Variable	Findability/Discovery
UC059	Data Consumer	Filter a data search	I can know which	Dataset	Findability/Discovery
UC060	Data Consumer	Filter a data search	I can know which	Variable	Findability/Discovery
UC061	Data Producer	Share data in a	Receive input and	Most/all	Curation/Deposit/Pres
UC062	Data Producer	Share data in a	Track and share	Most/all	Curation/Deposit/Pres
UC063	Repository	Provide a range of	So that the specific	Dataset	Findability/Discovery
UC064	Repository	Provide multiple access	To account for the	Most/all	Findability/Discovery

User Problems

Aligned

How to cite custom

How to deposit and cite

What granularity is most

ervation

ervation

ervation

etrics

etrics

ervation

ervation

ervation

ervation

ervation

ervation

etrics

ervation

etrics

ervation

Subscription access to

etrics

etrics

etrics

etrics

etrics

ervation

ervation

May fit multiple

Clinical studies require a

Clinical studies require a

Datasets are not always

A researcher's primary (or

A researcher's primary (or

A researcher's primary (or

Do metadata fields

Do metadata fields

Are datasets shared in an

Are datasets shared in an

However providing a

How to reflect granularity

Narrative

Serial #

N001

N002

N003

N004

N005

N006

N007

N008

N009

N010

N011

N012

N013

N014

N015

Narrative

the record to a relevant survey from a data repository. At the repository, they are able to view the list of variables in the study (and do some simple online with a DOI. They are now seeking to publish their research, and the journal is requesting they cite the data source directly. However, they only used part

No narrative; record use to identify source document used to create Use Cases (rather than a narrative per se).

No narrative; record use to identify source document used to create Use Cases (rather than a narrative per se).

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No narrative; record use to identify source document used to create Use Cases (rather than a narrative per se).

understand the reuse of research data) and then notes the types of user breakdowns that tend to be more useful (e.g., the geographic distribution of - "I am interested in this topic for our own born digital collections particularly the question of what level to assign the DOI (or other PID). I have wondered if A researcher realizes the data they collected could be useful to train and evaluate machine learning models. especially as they can change over time.

stem from a project (e.g., data, related publications, funder, etc.)

would like to find and assess possible datasets that meet their criteria in the most efficient way possible.

with each other (and having clarity on the different versions), we also would like to be able to open it up for public comments/questions/input/feedback.

varying informationa aboutgranularity, and data users use inconsistent granularity terms (e.g., may use "dataset" to mean different things).

browsing, filtering, etc.) and how people use them. But it is uncertain how best to reflect levels of granularity (collection, dataset, variable etc.) on the

Source (name & linked URL)

use case in my professional
theoretical use case

IG: Use Cases data [Data set].

<https://zenodo.org/record/5006525>

cases from the RDA Data Versioning
[Recommendations of the Working Gr](#)

Fenner M, Lowenberg D, Jones M,
Preservation Announcement and

DE theoretical use case

GS theoretical use case

Concept Definitions

Title	Definition
Roles	
Data Producer	specify what data will be collected, and determine how to analyze the data and draw conclusions
Data Consumer	data life-cycle and may use the data to verify published results, for secondary analyses or for
Data Subject	more broadly as individual entity measured by the data, e.g., organization, non-living individual,
Repository	data. Data repositories work with the data producers to ensure data remain useful over time and
Data manager/steward/curator	sure that data is properly managed, shared, and preserved. They have technical skills and
Publisher	Publishers and Journals are increasingly encouraging researchers to cite data, and some are
Funder	number of funding agencies require researchers to actively and properly manage their data
Government/Policy Maker	formulating research data and open science policies.
Research Administrator	administrative side of research, including the link between research activities and research
Most/all	

Levels of Granularity

Data point	One single measurement or result, e.g. a single number. Alternative term--datum.
Variable	A series of single values measured in the same way across all entities measured in the dataset, e.g.
File	One file with multiple measurements or results, e.g. a spreadsheet
Instrument (of data collection)	E.g., a particular sensor
Custom subset	A user-created selection of a part/parts of a dataset for a purpose
Dataset	A package of data deliberately published, typically comprised of multiple files, which would be repre
Custom combination	A user-created grouping of datasets or subset thereof (e.g., results from a search (w/its own resolv
Collection (of datasets)	A repository-created grouping of datasets (e.g., fixed in some way, collected for a thematic or admini
Most/all	

Category/Type of Use

Findability/Discovery	To find data, including both metadata and data, to be discovered by either humans or computers.
Access	To obtain data after successfully finding it, including issues of authentication and authorisation.
Interoperability	analysis, storage and processing. Or to integrate different data infrastructure systems.
Analysis	and recap, and evaluate data, so as to glean useful information which can then be used to make
Identification/Citation/Metric	data is to provide a reference to data in the same way as researchers routinely provide a
Curation/Deposit/Preservation	long-term data availability.
Most/all	

Notes (including source of concept/definition)

Coursera: "Research Data Management and Sharing" by The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill + addition

Coursera: "Research Data Management and Sharing" by The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill + addition
Data Curator's Roles and Responsibilities: An Introduction
Coursera: "Research Data Management and Sharing" by The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill + addition
Guangyuan Sun

<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-021-01820-8>

j. a column in a spreadsheet, a survey question and its possible response choice

represented by a record in a data catalogue

(e.g. a persistent URL), combined locally by the end user, etc.)

(for administrative reason)

Adapted from FAIR

Integrated from multiple sources from the web

Total	
	64

Role/Who	Total
Data Consumer	28
Data manager/steward/curat	2
Data Producer	10
Funder	1
Repository	22
Research Administrator	1
Grand Total	64

Category/Type of Use Case	Total
Access	9
Analysis	4
Curation/Deposit/Preservatio	16
Findability/Discovery	19
Identification/Citation/Metrics	12
Interoperability	1
Other	3
Grand Total	64

Note: this field was optional; may contain blank

Level of Granularity Involved	Total
Collection (of datasets)	4
Custom combination	4
Custom subset	19
Dataset	18
File	4
Instrument (of data collection)	1
Most/all	6
Variable	8
Grand Total	64

Total user problems identified	18
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Note: this field was optional; may contain blank entries

The following instructions were provided to Use Case authors regarding the standardized process for cr

Initials of Authors on the Use Cases List refer to the following Data Granularity Working Group Members:

SGY: Guangyuan Sun

GS: Graham Smith

RS: Rouven Schabinger

KM: Katherine McNeill

DE: David Elbert

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